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Deviant Behaviours Among Students: The Role Of The Teacher and Implication for Counselling

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates deviant behavior among secondary school students, the role of teachers, government, school, and parents. Causes of deviant behaviors, effects and characteristics of deviant behaviors, recommendations and counseling implications, conclusions were mentioned in the study.

Keywords: deviant behavior, student, counseling, non-criminal behavior

INTRODUCTION

The disciplines of psychology and sociology have both evolved as distinct disciplines that investigate and explain the patterns of behaviors exhibited by individuals and groups respectively (Agwanwo and Badey, 2021). They have developed as a by – product of the biological, psychological, environmental or social creations of individuals in society. These socially-constructed behaviors are woven around the norms and values of a group, community or society, whose members are supposed or expected to follow; and are thus recommended whenever they so do. The acceptance of a group or society’s laid-down rules and regulations is what makes it possible for social order to prevail in such a society or group (Agwanwo and Onyige, 2021).

However, even though it is expected that a group, an organization or members of a society are duty-bound to adhere to the established norms and values in their daily social engagements, it is often the case that some members of the group or society are found to deviate from socially prescribed standard of behavior. As a matter of fact, human behavior orbits around two general parallel lines, the acceptable or the non-acceptable behavior, the pro-social or the anti-social behavior, the conformist or the non-conformist behavior, the criminal or the non-criminal behavior and the deviant or the non-deviant behavior. Indeed, deviant behavior has been known to be part and parcel of all-known civilizations, past and present; and it has always been a major source of concern to individuals, groups and society at large (Stanley, 2016).

In fact, in spite of the challenges it poses to the normal functioning of the society, Durkheim, Agwanwo and Onyige (2021) contended that deviant behavior is an unavoidable, normal and integral part of all healthy social existence. Durkheim’s position is borne out of the fact that regardless of the prescribed normative standards in place, no society has been capable of achieving the feat of making all her members conform to their social norms. Hence, the acquiesced normality of deviant behavior, which manifestations, however, differs from one social setting to another and also in time and space as well.

Deviant behavior, as a matter of fact, is a behavior that is not consistent or that is at variance with the prevailing norms and values in a particular social setting. However, the deviation of human conduct from socially accepted norms could be in the positive or negative. Position deviance is one that over-conforms to the norms and values of the society. In fact, it is a form of deviation that positively exceeds the

normative standards of a society (McClelle & Beggan, 2017). On the other hand, negative deviance is a form of social deviation from the acceptable norms of the society. This form of deviance impacts negatively on a society. It destabilizes or creates social disorder in the society. This research work examines negative deviance within the context of the socially – prescribed norms, rules and values that make for the smooth functioning of the society.

Agwanwo and Onyige (2021) defined deviant behavior as any form of behavior that deviates from the prevailing acceptable pattern of behavior. The world over all civilizations, cultures, and indeed, societies-past and present-have distinct deformed sets of prescribed norms, values, and rules that have evolved over time within such a group. And so, members making up such a group norms are expected to observe such group norms. Therefore, naturally, the violation of this shared socially – prescribed pattern of behavior always results in negative reactions, disapprovals and even sanctions by the majority of the persons who share these norms that are violated.

Anderson and Taylor in Ameachi-Ani and Igwe (2021) defined deviant behavior as behavior which breaches commonly held norms, values and expectations of the society. Anderson and Taylor in Ameachi-Ani Igwe (2021) further stated that those who depart from the conventional norms are called deviants. Steven (2013) observed that deviant behavior is seen by lots of people as bad because it constitutes a social interactions and impairs social organizations. Jones (2016) perceived deviant behavior as behavioral disposition which is not in accordance with the norms and ideals of a particular society. Hastings and Thomas in Nicholas and Kennedy (2018) defined deviant behavior as any behavior that is recognized as violating expected rules and norms.

Deviant behavior poses a real threat to the physical and social survival of an individual within certain social environments such as the family and the school. Deviant behaviors can be seen in various forms regardless of age or gender. Ameachi-Ani and Igwe (2021) identified the following negative behaviors as deviating and unacceptable to the society: lying, bullying, fighting, violent behaviors, gambling, quarrelling, disobeying teachers, running away from homes, prostitution, murders, rape, burglary, domestic violence, drug abuse, etc. students in tertiary schools in rivers state often engage in anti-social behaviors such as cult related activities, bullying, examination malpractices etc. most of these students engage in deviant behaviors because of psycho-social factors such as low self-esteem, external locus of control, family type and socio-economic status of parents.

Psycho-social variables are factors related to deviant behavior or anti-social behavior among undergraduates in institutions of higher learning. The psychological variables are the self-esteem and locus of control of students in institution of higher learning. Self-esteem refers to our positive and negative evaluation of ourselves (Fein, 2015). The above definition sees self-esteem as positive or negative assessment or evaluation of oneself. Myers (2017) defined self-esteem as a person's overall self-evaluation or sense of self-worth. The definition means that the evaluation of ourselves gives us sense of self-worth. For instance, if we see ourselves as being attractive, athletic, smart, and destined to be rich and lived, it will make it to have high sense of self-worth or self esteem. Thus psychologists are of the view that if we want to help people feel better about themselves, we should first make them feel better attractive, athletic, smart, etc. Students could have both positive and negative self-esteem and they have major implications on deviant behavior among students in institutions of higher. Onukwufor (2012) noted that people with positive self-images tend to be happy, healthy, productive, and successful. They are also confident bringing to new challenges a wining and motivation attitude, which leads them to persist longer at difficult tasks, sleep better at night, maintain their independences in the face of peer pressure and suffer few ulcers. This goes to show that students with positive self-esteem are productive and hardworking and confident bringing to new challenges a wining and motivating attitude and when these qualities are present in the students they may not indulge in violating the standards and norms of the school by engaging in examination malpractice and social vices.

Onukwufor (2012) also noted that people with negative self-images tend to be more depressed, pessimistic about the future, and prove to failure. They lack confidence; they bring to new tasks a losing attitude that traps them in a vicious self-defeating cycle. People with low self-esteem do not trust their

own positive self-appraisals (Joseph et al, 2003). And when they fail, they tend to blame themselves which makes them to feel even less competent (Brockner, 2016). Students with negative self-esteem tend to be depressed, prone to failure, are pessimistic about the future and they may indulge in behaviors that are not generally acceptable. Locus of control is one psychological variable that predisposes the student to deviant behavior.

Locus of control refers to the extent to which people perceive outcomes as internally controllable by their own efforts and actions or as externally controlled by chances or outside forces (2017). People with internal locus of control attribute their successes and failures to internal factors such as personal effort, skill or behavior while those with external locus of control attribute their successes and failures to external factors such as chance, luck, fate, or actions of powerful others such as teachers. Those who see themselves as internally controlled are more likely to do well in school, successfully stop smoking, and delay instant gratification in order to achieve long term goals (Miller et al, 2018). The students who have external locus of control blame their poor grades on things beyond their control, such as blaming teachers, poor books and parental negligence and when that happens they may indulge in behaviors that are not generally accepted in the school system.

Social variables are also related to deviant behaviors of students in institutions of learning. The social variables related to deviant behavior of undergraduate students are family type, parent's socio-economic status, residence, and peer influence. Researchers have attributed the causes of deviant behavior in tertiary schools to student's poor family background s, family size, and peer influence, residence and social pressure/influence and personality dysfunctions. Echebe (2010) observed that students who come from abusive parents display characteristics of abusive persons. Such children for instance end up beating their fellow playmates without feeling any kind of remorse. On the other hand, students brought up by uncaring parents usually portray delinquent behaviors. They resort to criminal activities to achieve what they could not get from their parents. Charon (2017) is of the view that such students take part in criminal activities such as stealing, rioting/rebellion among others. In the same vein, mass media has a negative effect on school children, more specifically the violent content that are aired in the television or in cinemas. It is believed that children believe what they see in the media more than what happens in the real life (Dibia & Nicholas, 2017). Undergraduate students who watch too many fights in the television or read pornographic materials on the internet begin to develop certain characteristics that affect the people around them negatively. The society also models the behavior of people. The attitude that other people have concerning their fellow human race leads to rebellion from the marginalized groups. Such people who are neglected by the society, and whose needs are not looked into by the people in authority end up engaging in activities or behavior that contradicts the requirements of the society. Frustration from these is now being expressed through hostage taking, vandalism and kidnapping (Nicholas et al., 2015). The school learning environment is a place where children go to get education and to learn all sorts of good mannerism. It however turns out that children get negatively affected by their fellow children in school. Some develop deviant behaviors after watching the way their peer behaves.

Boobies and Elhaney (2015) reported that deviant behavior is enacting of indiscipline or behavior disorder which serves as a major source of social vices. In schools these days, evidence has shown that the anti social behaviors of children are now rampant. There is evidence that an individual learns to think in a way as his group defines thinking that is why we now experience cultism, dropout of schools, gambling, bullying of teachers, truancy, smoking, drugs, students unrest and acts of diligence among others. In most universities, it has been observed that one of the factor traceable to causes of deviant behaviors of students in family type, parenting style and home background. (Bindag et al., 2015) stated that peer groups are primary groups of people who have similar the interest, age, background or social status that are likely to influence the person's beliefs and attitudes.

Owuamana and Bankole (2015) opined that peer influence is also family identified in different types of communication styles which lead to bullying among the students. Family is the first social environment the child finds himself. Clifford (2021) maintained that family remains the primary environment of the child. Clifford (2021) emphasized that family environment has more chances of increasing or decreasing

the intellectual achievement of the child. Akubue and Okolo (2018) defined family as a small kinship structural group with the key function of natural socialization of new born. Similarly, in Okunniyi (2014), family is defined as a primary social group of parents, offspring and possibly other members of the household. Family refers to all the conditions and circumstances in the family which influence the child physically, intellectually and emotionally (Muola, 2010). Children coming from different family backgrounds are affected differently by such family condition that is why some children have good family background while some have poor background. Fleege in Eke (2019) noted that with some families, the background may vary from time to time for the same individuals. Formal education therefore remains the vehicle for human development which must start from the family. There are different categories of families. The major categories of families in the words of Anderson and Taylor (2010) includes: Traditional families-where the father is the major breadwinner and mother at home rearing children; divorced families - families that have been reconstituted following the breaking of marriage; single parent families – likely headed by women; step families-with new siblings and new parents stemming from re-marriage.

Again, Carlos (2012) stated that parents directly influence their children's behavior through the parenting styles. The family has an indirect and direct control over their children, e.g. smoking, drinking, of alcohol. Female undergraduate students tend to act out as a result of low level of support from their mother while boys tend to act out as a result low level of parenting monitoring. In a study of Ajake et al., (2018) child rearing style is a function of family socio economic status. Significant difference exists between respondents from autocratic child rearing family and those from democratic homes in lying, stealing and truancy. Also, in a study carried out by Eshiet (2002) he discovered that students from higher educational parent's background performed significantly better than those from low educational backgrounds.

A family is a place where a person or group of persons has adopted as a living place. Greg (2011) described that the home is a living space used as a permanent or semi-permanent residence for an individual, family, household or several families. The family is made up of humans; usually with parents and their offspring. It is usually a place in which an individual or a family can rest and be able to store personal property. Family environment refers to aspects of people's domestic lives that contribute to their living conditions. These factors may be physical (poverty, psychological conditions due to parenting; social circumstance (living alone) or wider cultural patterns of life related to the location (suburban environments, urban environments (Loeber in Amadi & Nnuba, 2021). Family environment has been theorized to have serious impact on the behavior of children including deviant behavior. Residence is also a sociological factor that can predispose the individual to deviant behavior in society. Where the student lives matter a lot to his students or her overall behavioral development. Stephen (2018) observed that students who live in slums and ghettos are very likely to become deviants in society. The environment plays a major role in influencing the behavioral and personality development of the individual. Therefore, there is need to investigate psycho-social variables and deviant behavior of year one students in Rivers State Universities.

Deviant Behaviour

Deviant behavior can defined as not keeping to rule and norms of the society or schools. Deviant behavior is an emerging issue among undergraduate students in tertiary schools. It is a global phenomenon, posing a serious threat. In a society such as ours, not only parents that train and influence a child, the society and environment in which he/she lives exert some measures of influence. Deviant behaviors in children include those acts or attitudes that deviates from normal behaviors expected of children, and which negate moral standards (cui & Fincham, 2010). These behaviors are usually unacceptable in the immediate society. There are numerous behaviors that can be classed as negative amongst children depending on the situation and activity, including lack of initiative, being irresponsible, aggression and playing the victim Kel in Amadi and Nnubia (2021). These negative behaviors can apply to work, learning habits or even dealing with things like addiction. Some commonly known negative behaviors in children include lying, stealing/puffery, bullying, gangsterism, defiance, disrespectful behaviors, substance abuse, aggression,

school absenteeism etc. these attitudes have negative impacts on the development of the children, and can determine the level of wellbeing for both the child, especially parents.

Deviant behavior has been described as a behavior that is at variance with acceptable norms of a school (Peretomode, 2011). It is a negation of school rules and regulations, norms and values of a group or an institution. Any conduct or act that violates the laws or acceptable standards of a society or group is described as deviance. Deviant behavior is an act or conduct that does not conform to established rules of a society or group (Bolu-Steve, 2017). What is considered deviant behavior varies among different societies. Thus a behavior may be acceptable by a society but considered deviance by another society. In addition, Igbino in Idris (2016) maintained that deviance among students could be a way of drawing attention of injustice, and to expose a system's defects so that they can be fine-tuned. As expressed by Suleiman (2011) three elements make behavior to be described as deviance. These elements are: behavior that impedes an individual's effective functioning in the society, behaviors that hinder an individual meeting his/her personal needs and behavior that interferes negatively with the wellbeing of other members of the society.

Ali et al, (2014) found that students' misconduct was high in Lagos state secondary schools. Students' poor performance in external examinations was attributed to factors such as lack of facilities, indiscipline and administrative malfeasance among principals (Mbaabu & Orodho, 2014). Cheng, (2012) attributed deviant behavior of students to student-teacher relationship and family social economic status. Yaman and Uygumada (2019) stated that teachers adopt passive learning strategies when the classroom is overcrowded, this breeding ground for deviant behavior. This situation slows down learning progress (Earthman, 2012). Discipline in the school is the concern of education stakeholders worldwide. In the United States of America, 40% of teachers have left the teaching profession due to disruptive behavior problems (Mtsweni, 2018). He maintained that many teachers in American schools have sought transfer to schools with less behavior problem, thus making some schools to be left in the hands of unskilled novice teachers. Smith (2016) explained that unruly behavior of high school students and rampant cases of violence have led to exodus of urban school teachers to rural schools. A single act of unruly behavior can have a lasting impact on student learning (Mezrgui, 2015). Ali, and Gracey (2013) noted that improved teacher-student relationship is important for building a noise-free classroom learning environment. Therefore, university authorities and lecturers have major roles to play in ensuring that a trouble-free school environment is created for improved connectedness, security and safety of students and better learning outcomes.

Deviant behavior varies from one society to another. It is obvious that what might be seen normal behavior in another community might be seen abnormal in another. For example, in the northern parts of the country covering body is a very big culture and it is highly respected as their tradition demand but, in the southern region it is not allowed while because it is against the ethics of our cultures (Roberts, 2016). But it is their style of dressing and cannot be violated, if one does it has become a deviant behavior and that person will be sanctioned or kill as their culture permits in their north. However, deviant behavior should be stamped out to allow development and growth. Opong (2018) states that deviant behavior is a disease that is against transparency, justice and fair play.

The word "deviant" means different thing from what most people seem to be acceptable and normal. This implies a deviation from clearly defined norms. Angel (2015) defined deviant behavior as any behavior that lacks conformity and acceptability of people in the society. Deviant behavior describes an action or behavior that attracts punishment or sanctions in the society or school. Diche (2016) posited that deviant behavior is a behavior that violates the laid down rules and regulation of a given organization or group. He also emphasized that deviant behavior is a common phenomenon in the life of every human being but, stressed that it is rampant among students in schools which has led them in joining secret cults, and other heinous crimes in the school. Deviant behavior as a case study among students have the institutions as a home of thinking among parents and students because of manifestation of crimes being committed by them.

Types of Deviant Behavior in our School System

Ibuchim (2016) identified the following as types of deviant behavior in our school system.

Examination Malpractice: it is an unholy or barbaric act perpetrated by the students, examines and other agents during and after examination with intention to have undue advantage and earn unmerited grade. Most students in our school at various levels indulge or delve into malpractice which is against the examination act of 1999 which prescribed rules and sanctions but yet students also continue to live by it. The poor performance of students nationwide was as a result of examination malpractice in our schools.

Bullying: it is an aggressive behavior and is a behavior intended to hurt (Paschal, 2015). Bigger, stronger students always lord it over the smaller or tender ones. Okechukwu (2016) enumerated various forms of bullying such as assault, extortion and verbal humiliation. Most students involve in bullying each other in our schools with the intention of subduing them physically.

A bully is someone who uses his or her ability and strength to threaten or hurt those who are smaller and weaker sometimes the bully uses words to intimidate his or her victims. Pepler and Craig (2010) observe that bullying is the most common form of violence permitting the most powerful to dominate the less powerful. These researchers were of the opinion that bullying start at very young and small age, it is or push during kindergarten recess or some name callings. Rana (2014) maintained that bullying has two key components: repeated harmful act and an imbalance of power. Bullying involves repeated physical, verbal or psychological against a victim who cannot properly defend him or herself because of size, strength or because the victim is less psychologically resilient. Bullying is a type of aggressive behavior to hurt the weaker ones. Bullies are everywhere, at school, at home, on the street and even the church and mosque. Such people take delight in making others cry. They do not really need any reason to do that. Most of the common types of bullying include: kicking, beating, biting, threats, locking the victim inside a room, insects, harsh teasing, gossip and making unreasonable demands etc. Behavioral skills of self-control and social skills are acquired to stop it. Ekpo (2016) observed that bullying is an environmental issue not learnt but can be unlearned. This implies that with appropriate individual and group counseling in school is likely to control bullying. The home could be a centre of bullying. The implication is for counselors to investigate the family environment just like the school will be in a better position to identify the source of bullying within the school setting. It is possible to inform parents of their wards' common school bullying behaviors. Family counselling will also help in curbing school bullying. Parent's involvement could be visit to homes or discussions during Parents Teachers Association (PTA) special meeting. Monitoring and supervision or student against bullying will go a long way towards modifying the youths' behavior. Senior students should be enlightened on their obligations towards the junior ones. Orientation on the consequences of bullying should be intensive.

Truancy: This means being away from home and school during school hours. Truancy is a situation where a child stays away from school without good reason. Truancy is a deliberate absence from school, without a valid reason (Nwoye, 2014). The deliberate absence and without a valid reason presupposes that a child causes the absenteeism no matter the reason he has. For instance, if a child who is targeted is afraid of bullying and stays away from school, would this be regarded as a valid reason? A child has needs like play and if this forces him to be absent from school, would this be a valid reason? The fault of this definition is that valid reason is subjective. So the question is, without whose valid reason? No child lacks personal valid reasons for being absent from school. The school and parents may however, not regard such a child's valid reason as valid. Invariably, truancy could be defined as a child's poor attendance to school not on account of the child's ill health and family or school approval. Longe in Anyin (2015) defines truancy as "absence from school without permission, leaving school without authorization and evading specific lessons, probably typical of adolescent rebellion, self-assertion and reaction over certain developmental and psychological problems". Truancy starts from being absent from school with adequate knowledge of the parents and or significant other and one's poor attention to school. Odomeliam and Ajoku (2016) explained that truancy is a situation where a pupil loiters, wanders, and idles about, gallivants, rigmaroles, walks about and perambulates while lessons are progressing in the class. This explains why such children can leave home for school without reaching there. To modify

truancy, psychological needs (such as love, affection, protection, independence, freedom, adventure, exploration, and self-esteem among others) which are the foundation of truancy should be deployed.

Psychologically, Tor-Anyin (2015) suggested cognitive restructuring for dealing with the problem of truancy among students. Cognitive restructuring is a psychological concept that requires appealing to the mental capability of an individual to have his/her thinking on an issue re-examined. Counsellors must liaise with parents to get the roots of truancy by examining the various needs of the child in the given psychological environment. Both parties must work together in order to create some motivations for children since lack of school motivation can also cause truancy among youths. For effectiveness, avoid sarcastic comments, scolding, lecturing, punishing and preaching. This is because the intimidations accompanying threats are not always efficacious and irrelevant. It rather impedes the willingness of such individuals to open up. Self-reporting techniques could also help the truant to drop the practice. Self-reporting or self-regulating is the setting of goals, evaluating one's performance and adjusting to meet the goal in the content of on-going feedback (Odoemelan, 2017). This democratic process will help truants to adjust positively to schooling. Capitalize on the truant's ambitions and future and allow him/her to visualize the future if the truancy continues. This can be done through adequate information. Identify goals and how to work towards the goals and use behavioral contact. The child could equally visualize the life of the park touts and write about their future as compared to counseling strategies for modification of deviant behaviors among youths and their age mates who are in school. The psychological approach to the treatment of truancy is likely to produce better results than scolding, denial of love or food, corporal punishment, suspension and expulsion from school.

Stealing: this involves stealing fellow student's or school properties. Stealing is simply the act of taking another person's possession by deceit or without permission or express approval. The mention of expression implies that stealing could involve material and non – material things. According to Tor-Anyin (2015) material things include books, food stuff, clothes, money any other physical things. While non – material things include mental aspects like dishonest, taking of another person's work as yours or sneaking in without notice to obtain information with the aim of causing harm or advantage for self or agent. Deceit involves taking something that belongs to another person furtively, scrumptiously or through trickery. Stealing, cuts across age, gender, marital status, literacy level, socio-economic levels, the lower, middle and high. Thus, Lar (1995) reported stories of burglaries and similar cases of theft committed by children of professors and lecturers. Children from low professional occupations were however found to be more involved in stealing than others, probably because parents in low professional occupations do not have money to care of their needs and so their off springs steal to meet urgent demands. However, children from the upper class families are not exempted as peer's group membership influences is usually strong. Kingsley (2015) explained that most students indulge in the habit of taking what does not belong to them. This behavior if not checked could give rise to other abnormal behaviors in a student and affects their academic performance.

Lateness to School: Pere (2014) explained that there is prescribed time for resumption of school but some students often come to school late when morning assembly is over and in some cases, when the teacher is already in the class teaching. This leads to distraction.

Drug Abuse: This means indiscriminate use of drugs without doctor's prescription or use of drugs other than their purpose. Chamberlin (2015) posited that students in school and adults outside the school setting have been found smoking; Indian hemp, heroine, cigarette and other drugs not prescribed by doctors to feel 'high' shine their eyes, to commit various dangerous crimes or to feel bold to talk with their teacher or the opposite sex.

Sex Offences: This involves various degree of sexual misconduct exhibited by students which include masturbation, lesbianism, homosexual, premarital sex, abortion. This affects their academic performance or lead to school dropout.

Absenteeism: Staying away from school for no reason or without permission. Most students absent themselves from school without the permission of the school authority and his affect their performance in school.

Lateness: Lateness is a social problem that attracts the attention of the school authority; lateness is coming to school not on time. Pupils and students (youth) come late to school, class, lecture hall, games, work etc. coming late to school, work, mosque etc. the Nigerian youths are expected to come to school or work at a specified time limit. Behavioral skills of counting, frequency and graphing are mastered to draw base rate of lateness prior treatment. The counselor would train the pupil's and students (youth) the skills of self-control, self-monitoring and self-management. The counselor needs to inform the youth/parents, the importance of punctuality, and parents should wake children early and keeping their time through the use of alarm clock is important.

Quarrelling and Fighting: Psychologists regard quarrels as cathartic (i.e., helping the people quarrelling to off-load their grievances) and didactic (i.e., helping the people quarrelling to learn what others think about them), yet quarrels are not a healthy development. When quarrels are not controlled, they usually escalate into physical fights. In school, work or home, quarrels generate ill feelings, bad blood and thus, weaken interpersonal co-operation and relationship.

Fighting is an aggressive behavior and involves muscle flexing, exchange of blows, beating, battering of women or domestic violence. Some may even faint as result of fighting. Some who fight with rods, chain and mortars have killed their opponents. The guidance counselor should use the behavioral counselling technique to discourage quarrelling or physical fighting.

Disobedience/Insubordination: this is refusal to obey either at school or at home. It is also called indiscipline or defiance, while insubordination refers to rebellion, defiance and ungoverned ability. A disobedient and insubordination youth or child is somebody who does not obey his teacher, parent or elder, and one who does not easily follow the ruler ship of the teacher, parent and elder. The teacher's instruction and teaching are not accepted by the youth. The Guidance Counselor should develop skills of persuasion and encouragement to apply so that the youth will be draw back to the teacher, parent and elder.

Cultism: Secret cult is referred to as a system of worship that is expressed in rituals and which is kept from the views of others except the cult members. Members concentrate in cult language which is peculiar to them. The secret cult members carry out their heinous activities in the night. The federal Government of Nigeria (1999) defines cultism or secret society as: an organized group with its own ideology, and objectives, which are only known to their members.

Most secondary school students joint secret cult societies in school in order to make up for their deficiencies either academically, socially or economically (Akinboye, 2015).

Cultism occurs when group of students come together under one name with bad intention of intimidating fellow students to join them or disturbing the activities of the school for their evil objective (Chima, 2015). According to him most students involves in cultism to compensate their academic inadequacy. It is a major misbehavior and the after effects of their activities do no one any good.

Cheating: Cheating means deceiving or tricking people or acting in dishonest way to again advantage over people. Denga (1998) opined that cheating may take place within and outside the school.

Cheating in the school is often referred to as malpractice. The importance attached to grades and academic certificates make youths engage in cheating in order to earn good grades for a certificate that can merit a job or further education for them. Cheating out of school may occur in business transactions, family relations and even between members of the church or mosque. Those who cheat may enjoy some temporary gain or get away with offences, but cheating is a vice and not a virtue. Youths must be taught in school, at the family level, in the church/mosque and through the mass media to shun cheating. The guidance counselor can modify this undesirable behavior among youth and Nigerian workers even our leaders by organizing occasional seminar and talks using the cognitive restructuring technique.

Lying: Lying is the act or practice of telling or speaking falsehood; it is an act which when repeated often becomes a habit. Quite often, lying is resorted to as a cover up for some misdeeds or pranks. Youth often tell lies to the teacher, parents, and school authority to avoid being punished for wrong doings. The guidance counselor should explain and educate such individual on the danger of lying, insist on honesty, praise him/her every act very act of honesty and reassure him/her of unconditional love the misconduct.

Examination Malpractice: the issue of examination malpractice is not new in our schools. Ogbodo (2016) stated that examination malpractices is any act of wrong doing or neglect that contravenes the rule of acceptable practice before, during the and after an examination by body in any way is tantamount to malpractice. Maisamari by (2005) stated that examination malpractice is seen as “misconduct or improper behavior by a candidate or any nod or anybody any body in or after examination thereby contravening the stipulations rules and for and regulations for the examination”. Hence in order to regulate life in our school as a whole, set of simple rules and regulations are in force. Oparaku (2015), observe that examination malpractice is an activity which reduces students (youth) ability in educational achievement from primary, secondary and tertiary institution. It is a fraudulent method of obtaining or scoring marks are not merited or deserved. It is an art of indiscipline or improper practice which student (youth) employ to score high marks in order to impress people. The guidance counselor should counsel them on responsibility, good morals, positive study behaviors, hard work, determination and dedication to studies to avoid a fraudulent method of passion examination.

Indecent Dressing: Some people regard the way youths dress, particularly female as indecent while others argued that they are free to dress the way they deem fit because we are in a free society (Okwuaishu, 2015). The girl dresses skimpy and short, transparent with spaghetti hands. The dresses expose their sensitive bodies because they are immodestly and nakedly dressed. They are seduced or harassed by people of the opposite sex. Odoemelam (2017) says that the outcomes of indecent dressing are the following: fornication, self-abuse, pregnant prematurely and commit abortion, sell their bodies for money (both male and female prostitutes), adultery, rape, assault, and touching and holding hands in the public. Guidance counselors should train in skills of teaching about the danger of indecent dressing and set to youths, train girls. Indecent dressing means putting on cloth that shows part of the body that is not covered. It is a behavior that is a thought to be morally offensive on how to be assertive and how to say no, (refusal skills.) behavioral counselor should use songs (zip up, say no, no, no, etc.). Talk to them on the consequences of indecent dressing and sexually transmitted diseases (STDA), HIV/AIDS.

Smoking and Drinking Alcohol: Smoking of cigarettes is often associated with drug addicts since some of the drugs are in the form of shredded leaves or other substances that are usually wrapper up in papers and smoked like cigarettes. While drinking alcohol is a perpetual activity of those who are mostly members of any cult. These cultists, as they are called drink all forms of alcohol to stimulate them. Smoking and alcoholism are currently topical issues. In some decades back it was unheard that children and youth smoked or went to bar drink to beer and ogogoro (hot drink). Today some children and youths smoke as a gang, their peers and idle adults encourage them. They smoke and drink alcohol openly in bars, hotels and motels. Additionally, they are told to bring their parents/guardians by school management to sign undertaking of good behaviors for their wants. Destruction, has certain goals or causes which according to Nwoye (2017), include, the need for attention, reaction to feelings of rejection, anger, a need for power or revenge as well as envy and hatred (Tor-Anyin 2015). The guidance counselor should identify a model for emulation and provide resource persons for discussion. Modeling is as process by which a client learns and performs a behavior or response by observing counseling strategies for modification of deviant behaviors among youths and internalizing some aspects of a models performance (Akinade, 2013). Having identified their model, they should follow a discussion on how such model's characteristics can be imbibed.

Characteristics of individuals with Deviant Behavior

The following are the behavioral disorder of deviant youths or students:

- Inappropriate types of behavior or feeling under normal conducts.
- A general pervasive mood or unhappiness or depression.
- A tendency to develop physical symptoms pains or fears associated with personal or school problems.
- An inability to learn which cannot be explained by intellectual sensory or health factors.
- An inability to build or maintain satisfactory interpersonal relations with peers and teachers.
- Ability to live a scheduled life is their watchword.

- They are always temperamental and cannot reason normal.
- They do not interact freely with people.
- They always aim high and cannot concentrate in life.
- They see the world as a place of do or die place.
- They always join opposition.
- They are catalyst and cannot be loyal to the lawful authority.
- Their existence is a threat to people who are reasonable.
- They are people who are at logger head with their people.

Causes of Deviant Behavior among School Students

Family background: The home a child is born and brought up can cause a child to exhibit deviant behaviors in school. The home or family background encompasses family socio-economic status. Child rearing practices etc. for instance, an over permissive home exposes the child to all kinds of behaviors including deviant behavior. Chuks (2016) posited that other factors within the home like broken family, and poor parental relationship are capable of breeding children that misbehave in school.

Biological factors: these includes genetic factors such as psychopath (inherited antisocial behavior), brain damage. Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is a neuron behavioral developmental disorder primarily characterized by the “co-existence of attention problems and hyperactivity with each behavior occurring infrequently alone”.

Influence of Mass Media: Exposure to bad television programmes, immoral magazine as well as pornographic films and materials, makes students to be involved in immoral behavior. Kento (2015) observe that the effects of unwholesome mass media seem to have negative impact on the character development of children than their positive impression. The students find it difficult to adjust to good personal, vocational, educational and social demands.

Societal Factors: Societal factors are one of the problems subjecting students into deviant behaviors. As society experience growth and become complex, so do societal factors causing student deviant behavior. The increase in deviant behavior in our society today cannot be overemphasized. Onyejiaku (2010) brought forward psychological factors such as cognitive level and personality traits as factors that contributed to deviant behavior in our school.

Peer Group: it is also dynamic which has assisted in destroying our children. Peer pressure refers to the group an individual identifies his or her self with peer pressure refers to the influence exerted by a peer group in encouraging a person to change his or her attitudes, values or behavior in order to conform to group norms; most students indulge in deviant behavior in school because of influence of their peers.

Effects of Deviant Behavior

The following are the effects of deviant behavior:

- It affects teaching and learning as teachers spend more time trying to control students rather than teaching them.
- Most involved students don't benefit from schooling.
- It affects their academic performance because they are often into one deviant act or the other losing most vital class lessons.
- It leads to poor parent: Child relationship as most reasonable parent's withdraw their love and care on deviant children and also most deviant don't like coming closer to their parents because of fear of being hint.
- Deviant students often threaten their teachers, school authorities and even parents at home.

It leads to demonstration and destruction of school properties and in some cases deviant students observe frequent demonstrations in the face of little issues.

The Roles of Government in Controlling Deviant Behavior in our Educational System

Government should ensure the availability of guidance counselors in all the educational levels. This will help in directing students' attention positively and handling issues of personal social problems of students. Counselors should also help in organizing orientation programmes and other activities geared towards helping students to live a productive life in and outside the school setting.

- Government should provide enough recreational facilities in schools across the nation such as table tennis, volley ball. This will help students to channel their energy into meaningful venture.
- Government should ensure that monitoring teams discharge their duties effectively. As this will help in cross examination of activities of teachers and students for optimal result in the system.

The Roles of the School in Monitoring Deviant Behavior

- There should always be disciplining options and severe sanction on observe deviant students so as to serve as deterrent to others.
- There should be proper implementation of school rules and regulations in our various schools without fear or favour. Schools are "seeing thing and respond to the dynamics of society change.
- The school authorities should introduce some kind of reward to well behaved students and keep re-enforcing them. This will help to encourage good behavior among students.

School administrators should ensure that teachers are teaching well and instructional materials are applied. This will help in encouraging the learner to learn well.

The Roles Parents in Ameliorating Deviant Behavior in our Educational Systems

- Parents and guardians should always monitor the type of friend their children keep and act as role model. This they could do by encouraging their children to keep and associate themselves with good friends in and outside the home.
- Parents and guardians should always monitor the type of film, and reading materials their children are expected to and discourage bad materials.
- Parents and guardians should always provide children with their academic needs and monitor their usage properly; proper provision of children' academic needs such as study materials, food, transportation, clothing etc.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research work, the following recommendations were made:

1. Counselors should assist students to build up self-esteem and locus of control as they study effectively in school, irrespective of their sex and age.
2. Counselors should provide effective educational counseling to students to enable them succeed academically.
3. Parents should also boost the self-esteem of their children by providing their academic needs and other support for academic improvement.
4. Parents should be practically involved in the education of their children; they should adopt parenting styles that can nurture their children physically, emotionally, and spiritually.
5. School counselors should assist students in building self-esteem and helping self-esteem and helping students to deal with academic tasks.
6. The government should tackle the issue of deviant behavior among students in the school system seriously.

Implications for Counseling

Based on the research, the implications for counseling include the following:

1. The deviant behavior among students may be as result of variables outside the school environment. One of such variable includes the home related variables particularly family type and socio-economic status of parents.

2. Also, the result of the study has shown that both parents and teachers have roles to play in curbing deviant behavior among children. Dealing with the deviant behavior in society is a joint responsibility among parents and teachers.
3. Furthermore; it is important that both parents and teachers equip students with adjustment skills that will help them to behave normally in society.

CONCLUSION

The study investigates deviant behavior among secondary school students, also considered the role of teachers, parents, governments and the school, types of deviant behaviors in our school system was also mentioned in the study, characteristics of individuals with deviant behaviors were parts of the study. The causes of deviant behavior among secondary school students and effects of deviant behavior were part of the study, and recommendations and conclusions were drawn to complete the study.

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